

Production of unstructured geometry by GLOW for lattice transport calculations

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ABSTRACT

The DRAGON5 lattice transport computer code is currently used at *newcleo* for general fuel design and cross sections preparation for Lead-cooled Fast Reactors (LFRs). A detailed 2D layout reproducing the full core or a portion of it is a prerequisite to solve the Boltzmann transport equation by one of many *surface-oriented* solution techniques available in DRAGON5. These layouts can be constituted by the repetition of simple shapes or made of heterogeneous elements to replicate the complexity of the core structure. Properties, such as the material, must be assigned to the different zones of the 2D model to correctly setup the lattice calculation. *newcleo* has recently released on GitHub the Python package GLOW¹ (Geometry Layout Oriented Workflow) to support the construction of convex 2D core geometries with properties assignment. GLOW uses the Python Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) of SALOME to build and visualise the geometry layout, and to export the output file with the corresponding representation according to the surface-oriented geometry model of DRAGON5. This article presents an overview of GLOW functionalities for an user-friendly geometry building. The software design is briefly outlined from the construction of simple assemblies up to more complex layouts.

Keywords: GLOW, constructive solid geometries, DRAGON5, tracking, SALOME

1. INTRODUCTION

The accurate modelling of neutrons behaviour within nuclear reactors is an essential part of reactor physics and safety analysis. Lattice computer codes offer methods for the solution of the Boltzmann neutron transport equation, which describes the collective behaviour of neutrons inside a domain, e.g., a nuclear reactor. The discretised geometry of a reactor typically consists of several fuel pins arranged according to regular patterns to form Cartesian or hexagonal lattices. These lattices can be encapsulated in boxes to form assemblies, which then are grouped together to represent the entire reactor core. The space- and energy- dependent flux solution for a specific geometry permits to evaluate power profiles, reactivity feedback, and fuel depletion, which are essential for reactor design.

Among the many tools available for performing neutronic analyses, *newcleo* relies on the DRAGON5 lattice computer code [1, 2]. It provides advanced methods for the calculation of fuel elements and the preparation of cross-sections. In DRAGON5, the SALT: tracking module discretises the spatial domain by generating integration lines used to solve the transport equation either via the *Collision Probability Method* (PIJ), the *Method of Characteristics* (MOC) or the *Interface Current* (IC) method [3]. Tracking can be of two types: *isotropic* (also known as TISO), corresponding to a geometry with white boundary condition, and *specular* (also known as TSPC), corresponding to a convex geometry repeating to infinity via specular reflection, rotations, and/or translations.

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¹GLOW repository is available at: <https://github.com/newcleo-dev-team/glow>.

Despite the SALT: module of DRAGON5 being able to track almost any *surface-oriented* 2D geometry, DRAGON5 can only natively handle the generation of simple geometries built using a small set of pre-defined operations available within the GEOM: module. The G2S: module converts the native geometry layout to a *.dat* description file used by the SALT: module to perform the tracking [2]. This file is produced in a format similar to the input file used by the TDT (*Two- and Three-Dimensional Transport*) solver of APOLLO2, one of the first neutron transport lattice code to provide MOC capabilities [4, 5]. More complex layouts, made by combining surface elements via Boolean operations, cannot be produced by DRAGON5 natively; external tools based on *Constructive Solid Geometry* (CSG), a method for creating 2D/3D geometries from combinations of simple primitive shapes, are needed.

So far, several SALOME-based applications have been developed to address the generation of surface geometries, among the main ones we can cite SALOMON and ALAMOS [6]. SALOMON is a Python2-based application developed in 2001 by EDF that exploits the GEOM module of the SALOME platform, an open-source environment offering 2D/3D CAD modelling capabilities [7]. SALOMON relies on an XML-formatted input file with a specific structure containing the description of the lattice's geometry layout in terms of cells and materials associated to each closed region of the lattice. It allows users to export the geometric description *.dat* file for the TDT solver of APOLLO2. Currently, SALOMON's development seems no longer active, resulting in an obsolete tool. ALAMOS is an application based on a dedicated *Graphical User Interface* (GUI) developed by CEA for APOLLO3 that exploits the Python libraries offered by the SALOME platform [6]. In particular, it makes use of the MEDCoupling module of SALOME to build the geometries and apply meshes to them. The regions of the geometry can also be characterised in terms of material property maps. While ALAMOS can handle any kind of complex geometry layout, SALOMON can only deal with lattices made of Cartesian-type cells, thus greatly limiting its application. In addition, SALOMON does not provide any support to the construction of surface geometries by exploiting the most common Boolean operations, which, instead, are supported by ALAMOS. Unfortunately, ALAMOS, despite being a more complete tool than SALOMON, does not have an open-source distribution.

GLOW was developed by *newcleo* to offer an open-source alternative for the production of surface geometries through *Constructive Solid Geometry* (CSG) functionalities provided by the *Application Programming Interfaces* (APIs) of the GEOM module of the SALOME platform. In GLOW, complex surface geometry layouts are easily generated by positioning and overlapping simple shapes, each associated with different types of property maps, to replicate the structure of cells and lattices, and even of the entire core. In addition, Boolean operations are automatically applied when a specific portion of the layout is extracted.

A GUI is essential to provide the best user-experience possible. In this sense, GLOW relies on the SALOME graphical user interface (via the GUI module) to display the built geometries in the available 3D viewer. In addition to the basic functionalities offered by GLOW, users can also make use of the geometry-building functionalities of the GEOM module directly from the GUI. Eventually, the GLOW and GEOM functionalities can be used from within a Python script that runs in the SALOME framework.

Since DRAGON5 relies on the *.dat* description file of the *surface-oriented* geometry, GLOW collects the geometric and property information from the built layout to generate the needed file.

This work gives an overview of GLOW and of its main functionalities, which allow extending the type of geometries that the DRAGON5 lattice transport computer code can deal with. The definition of the geometries treated by GLOW is briefly presented in Section 2, while the needs and the logical structure of GLOW are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 illustrates some examples of use cases built in GLOW. Conclusions and future developments are given in Section 5.

2. GEOMETRY DEFINITION

The geometry layout of a core can be described by radial cuts along the reactor height, resulting in 2D views which are discretised using either Cartesian or hexagonal patterns forming lattices where each characteristic unit is a cell. Layouts that rely on regular, basic geometric shapes (such as polygons or circles), repeated to form uniform patterns, are referred to as *structured geometries* [6]. However, uniform patterns are typically not enough to replicate the heterogeneities of an entire core. In such cases, *unstructured geometries* are preferred. They are made by general surface elements having different shapes and dimensions. Their combination is obtained as the result of applying Boolean operations, such as cuts and unions. The GEOM module of SALOME provides all the CSG operations required to support general drawing.

From a topological point of view, GLOW enables the construction of geometry layouts by exploiting several entities of the GEOM module of SALOME. Among the many available, we can cite the *edge* (either a *segment*, a *circle* or an *arc-of-circle*), the *face* (a 2D area from one or two closed sets of edges) and the *compound* (a container grouping together several GEOM entities).

In GLOW, the base unit of a geometry layout is identified by a *cell*. Cells are built from a characteristic *surface*, either rectangular or hexagonal, which is described by a GEOM face. Several other surfaces can be positioned or overlapped to define the final layout of a cell by assembling the corresponding GEOM faces into a GEOM compound. This compositional approach is similarly applied to lattices. *Lattices* are constructed either by repeating adjacent cells in the 2D space or by superimposing additional cells and surfaces onto a predefined cell pattern to replicate holes or metallic enclosures. In this context, assemblies are defined by encapsulating the lattice within these metallic containers that provide structural integrity and spatial boundaries. The same construction principle naturally extends to full-core modeling, where fuel assemblies are spatially organised within a global lattice framework that captures the macroscopic geometry of the reactor. The placement of shapes within a cell or of cells within a lattice relies on Euclidean geometric transformations, such as translation and rotation. Assembling shapes or cells together relies on Boolean operations, such as union, intersection, cut and partitioning.

Since calculations on a portion of the geometry layout are expected to be computationally cheaper, symmetries should be considered whenever possible. The same Boolean operations, in particular cuts, are exploited to extract parts from an existing layout, thereby isolating the minimum portion of the geometry required to describe the entire pattern. As an example for a Cartesian lattice with a 180 degree reflection symmetry, the cut part would be half of the lattice.

All the areas (i.e. the GEOM faces) of a geometry layout can be associated with a set of predefined properties, such as the material. In GLOW, these areas are referred to as *regions* and can be visualised with a specific colour map for a single type of property. Regions are collected in GEOM compounds to describe the entire geometry layout. These GEOM compounds are meant to represent:

- the *technological geometry*, in which regions delineate areas each associated with a specific material;
- the *sectorised geometry*, which further subdivides the regions of the technological geometry into sectors and circular areas. This refined geometry is typically used to capture flux gradients arising from geometric heterogeneities.

3. SOFTWARE ANALYSIS AND ARCHITECTURE

Software engineering provides best practices for guiding code design, keeping the focus on user needs and identifying the best way to address them before the actual implementation phase. GLOW covers the basic needs for creating generic layout drawings and exporting the surface geometry in the same format required by the TDT solver of APOLLO2. Requirements are derived by conducting functional and logical analyses to get a suitable *logical architecture*. The latter involves decomposing the entire system into abstract logical components, each of which is associated with the fulfilment of one or more

functions. This structure provides a high-level view of the application, which can then be refined further in terms of modules and classes.

Figure 1 illustrates the relationships among the logical components of GLOW. Despite a logical distinction between the functionalities that support the geometry construction and its export, they both present a common dependency from the APIs of the SALOME modules. In particular, there is a dependency on the GEOM module, dedicated to operating on geometric objects, and on the GUI module, responsible for modifying the view with the built geometric objects [8]. A shared *SALOME interface* component wraps all the functions of the GEOM and GUI modules needed by most of the logical components of GLOW. The *geometry builder* component supports the construction and the visualisation of GLOW elements that concur in defining a geometry layout. It enables users to quickly access to the functionalities for describing specific basic surfaces, as well as cells and lattices/assemblies, and for operating on them. In addition, specific parameters related to the type of geometry (either full or partial, if any symmetry is applied) and to the type of tracking used by the SALT: module of DRAGON5 can be configured. Their choice directly influences the information on boundary conditions present in the output file. The *geometry export* component deals with generating the output file for the SALT: module. Given the layout to export and its setup, this component extracts all the geometric information about its constituting elements to fill in the file.

Figure 1. Simplified view of the relationships between SALOME and GLOW's logical components.

GLOW follows an *Object-Oriented Programming* (OOP) paradigm for addressing both the geometry building functionalities and the export ones of the corresponding logical components. The software design pattern adopted by GLOW is the *Model-View-Controller* (MVC). The MVC pattern involves three types of object. The *model* represents the application containing the data, the *view* provides its presentation to screen, and the *controller* defines how the user interface reacts to user input and modify the model [9]. In the context of GLOW, there is no explicit distinction between the model and the controller. Both the *geometry builder* and the *geometry export* logical components are part of the model; they provide the data related to the geometry layout, even though they serve for different purposes. In addition, the *geometry builder* provides the ways for the model to interact with the view. In this sense, the controller functionalities are embedded in the model. The classes that constitute the model, in fact, come with a set of methods to directly apply modifications to their internal data structure, to display their geometry elements in the view and to update their state from an external object, possibly built in the view. The user has complete control over the building workflow without needing to display anything in the view. In this sense, he can modify the model directly given the fact that the geometry layout can be generated by grouping the specific functionalities in a Python script run in the SALOME framework. The ability to produce a geometry by running a script is an important feature for automating sensitivity analyses. This script can be executed multiple times with different parameter values to generate slightly varied geometries. This allows for a more detailed investigation into how changes to the spatial configuration

affect the tracking, and consequently the transport solution.

Regarding the view, a specific implementation of a standalone GUI was found unnecessary as SALOME already provides all the required functionalities through its GUI. This GUI comes with widgets for creating generic geometric objects, an Object Browser listing all the created elements, a 3D viewer for displaying the geometry layouts and an embedded Python console for interacting with the functionalities provided by GLOW.

4. USE CASES & PERFORMANCE

Typically, fuel assemblies adhere to prescribed patterns, with PWR and BWR adopting a Cartesian layout, whereas VVER and fast reactors using a hexagonal grid. Independently from the fuel assembly type, a lattice is characterised in terms of its pattern and the cells is filled with. Alternatively, cells can be inserted in the pattern either one-by-one, by specifying the coordinates of the centre of the element in the grid to fill, or at groups, by indicating the number of rings of the pattern to fill with a given cell. The example provided in Figure 2a shows a typical PWR fuel assembly built with GLOW. Cells representing fuel rods and guide tubes are included in the Cartesian pattern; the lattice is encapsulated in a cell to model the entire fuel assembly. The generated layout presents a symmetry of one eighth; the isolated portion shown in Figure 2a thus provides the minimum portion of the assembly that is enough to conduct a tracking with the SALT: module. In addition, the geometry layout is displayed according to the sectorised geometry of its cells. Each cell type can have its own sectorisation: guide tube regions are subdivided into sectors while additional circles are introduced to refine their geometries. The same sectorisation and refinement logic is applied to fuel cells with a different number of sectors and refinement circles. In addition, a *windmill* representation is adopted in the corners. Regions are coloured according to a map that highlights the different materials present in the assembly.

BWR fuel assembly configurations still rely on a Cartesian grid, even though they present more complex layouts because of cruciform rods and central water channels. Figure 2b shows the sectorised geometry of the Limerick GE11 BWR fuel assembly [10] constructed with GLOW. Compared to the PWR case, this one highlights a heterogeneous layout obtained by superimposing cells with different dimensions and refinement of the fuel pin cells. Moreover, the lattice is framed in a structure with curved corners and parts to reproduce stiffeners. This structure is realised by overlapping three rectangular surfaces with rounded corners and then cutting out the parts that do not belong to the stiffeners. The whole box layout is inserted in an enclosing square which represents the water surrounding the fuel assembly, and a non-uniform Cartesian mesh is generated. The cells in the lattice represent the fuel pins and water channels. They differ in both layout and dimensions, as well as sectorisation and refinement. Figure 2b presents the result of displaying the sectorised geometry of all the lattice cells, along with the mesh applied to the box. This kind of layout would not be possible without relying on Boolean operations.

Figure 3 presents an example of the technological and sectorised layouts for one twelfth of an LFR fuel assembly. It features a hexagonal layout consisting of fuel pin cells and a central hexagonal channel for residual heat cooling. The lattice is framed in a box with stiffeners. Given the geometric description file produced by GLOW from the layouts in Figure 3, the accuracy of DRAGON5 calculations with this geometry was assessed by replicating the same geometry and comparing the results obtained with the Monte Carlo code OpenMC [11]. In DRAGON5, the technological geometry (Figure 3a) was used for the self-shielding calculation with Tone's method, while the sectorised geometry (Figure 3b) was adopted for the flux calculation using MOC with a 1962-group energy structure. Figure 4 shows the comparison between DRAGON5 and OpenMC in terms of relative errors on pin-by-pin 1-group production rate. The maximum observed error is approximately 0.15%, indicating very good agreement.

GLOW also includes the capability to construct colorsets. A colorset represents a heterogeneous geometry that is used in neutron transport calculations to account for strong neutron interactions between different regions. Typically, it describes a layout in which a highly absorbing component is placed close

Figure 2. Examples of sectorised Cartesian geometries with material colour map.

Figure 3. Different views for a hexagonal symmetry of one twelfth of an LFR assembly (S30) with material colour map. (a) Technological geometry. (b) Sectorised geometry.

Figure 4. Relative error map for pin-by-pin 1-group production rate.

to a fuel element, which represents the neutron source. Figure 5 illustrates an example of a colorset with a hexagonal symmetry of one-twelfth of a full colorset, which comprises a central control assembly surrounded by six fuel assemblies.

Figure 5. View of a hexagonal symmetry of one twelfth of a colorset (S30) with material colour map.

In GLOW, a geometry layout can be constructed either by running a Python script in the SALOME framework, or by executing specific GLOW commands directly in the SALOME GUI. The time taken to generate a geometry layout is directly influenced by repeatedly displaying it in the SALOME 3D viewer. Once a layout has been finalised graphically, the script can contain only instructions for assembling and exporting the layout, eliminating the overhead introduced by visualisation. Additionally, the complexity of the layout correlates directly with the number of Boolean operations, which affects the time required for the layout to be generated or displayed. Using the geometry layout in Figure 2b as a reference, assembling and visualising the different parts in SALOME using a Python script takes a few tens of seconds on a laptop with a 1.30 GHz CPU and 16 GB of RAM.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Lattice transport calculations are essential in the design and analysis of LFRs. DRAGON5 provides different methods to solve the neutron transport equation by means of MOC, PIJ, or IC methods, provided that a proper description of the geometry layout is used. To overcome the limitations of DRAGON5 native geometries, *newcleo* has developed GLOW, a Python-based application that uses the APIs of the GEOM module of SALOME and relies on Boolean operations. GLOW facilitates the generation of a broad variety of layouts, ranging from simple cells to the entire core, thus addressing both structured and unstructured geometries. All the Euclidean transformations and the Boolean operations available in the GEOM module can be accessed by calling the corresponding wrapping functions of GLOW or by applying the operations directly from the SALOME GUI. The geometry layout can then be exported to a *.dat* file in a format similar to the one used by the APOLLO2 TDT solver. The *.dat* file is used as input to the DRAGON5 SALT: module for producing tracking information in the DRAGON5 format.

Users can build a Python script and run it in the SALOME framework. The script contains all the instructions to assemble and export the geometry without involving its visualisation in the SALOME GUI. The modules of GLOW can be imported in a SALOME session and directly used together with the commands in the GUI; different representations of the resulting geometry layout can be displayed and the characteristics of each single region inspected in terms of colour maps. In addition to geometry building and exporting functionalities, several improvement points are expected to be developed in future releases. Among the many others, the support to a multicell surface formulation compatible with

the IC method, the enhancement of the geometry building performance and the assignment of materials directly from DRAGON5 libraries would lead to a more integrated support for the preparation of the configuration files for DRAGON5.

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